

Studies of some electron transfer reactions of bis(dihydrogentellurato)-argentate(III) : A kinetic and mechanistic approach

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Abstract : The review by Lancashire¹ on silver is devoted to a small section on kinetics and mechanistic aspects. Since then a great deal of work has been done on kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of different reducing substrates by silver(III) complexes. The present review deals with studies on some electron transfer reactions involving bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) and 37 reducing organic compounds in alkaline medium which focuses on investigations during the period 1992-2006. The reactions have been carried out under different experimental conditions. Kinetic results and activation parameters of different redox processes have been incorporated and analyzed. The reduction of silver(III) may occur by either one electron or one step two electron transfer process. Although the oxidations appear to proceed through outer-sphere electron transfer process in the rate determining step, the reduced species of silver(II) ultimately decomposes to give black silver compounds. Attempts have been made to compare the results obtained earlier with the oxidations of similar substrates by bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III).

Keywords : Electron transfer, kinetics and mechanism, bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III), reducing substrates.

Introduction

Silver is one of the abundant elements in earth crust and has been known from ancient times. It is a typical transition element and the ions readily form complexes resulting in the formation of extensive variety of coordination compounds. Biological and medicinal aspects of silver chemistry are well established¹. Silver salts are known to be powerful bacteriocides. Silver nitrate which is highly corrosive in nature has been used to remove warts and cauterize wounds. Silver sulphadiazine is effective as a topical application to prevent infections in serious burns victims.

Silver is known to exist in three different oxidation states^{2,3}, e.g. Ag^I (*d*¹⁰), Ag^{II} (*d*⁹) and Ag^{III} (*d*⁸). The oxidation states Ag^{II} and Ag^{III} are readily available although they are unstable in water. They exist only in insoluble compounds or complex species. However, in order to achieve limited stability it requires the presence of *N*-heterocycles, *N*-macrocycles or biguanides. The preparations of Ag^{II} and Ag^{III} complexes have also been carried out by either electrochemical or chemical oxidations. Much work has been done on the preparation and properties of different silver(III) complexes⁴⁻⁶. A number

of well defined crystalline compounds have been described. The silver complexes with higher oxidation state have been used as oxidizing agents in the syntheses of organic compounds.

The simplest species containing silver(III) is Ag(OH)₄⁻ which in 1.2 mol dm⁻³ OH⁻ is stable for 2 h. A kinetic study of the acid initiated reduction has been reported⁷. Moreover biguanides, substituted biguanides, ethylene bis(biguanide) has been found to complex and stabilize silver(III). Kinetics of oxidation of pyruvic acid by ethylene bis(biguanide)silver(III) in aqueous acidic media has been studied⁸. Pyruvic acid is oxidized to give MeCO₂H and CO₂ together with colorless solution of Ag⁺ ion. A one electron inner-sphere redox mechanism rather than an outer-sphere electron transfer between the redox partners has been proposed. In addition bis(dihydrogenperiodato)argentate(III) and bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) have also been prepared in stable state. A number of kinetic studies have been reported on the oxidation of some reducing sugars⁹, nitrilotriacetic acid¹⁰ and amino acids (viz. glycine^{11(a)}, β-alanine^{11(b)}, L-leucine^{11(c)}, L-isoleucine^{11(d)} and L-proline^{11(e),(f)}) by diperiodatoargentate(III). In the oxidation of the reducing

sugars⁹ the participation of the open chain form of the sugar and a mechanism involving the initial formation of a complex between enediol of the sugar and Ag^{III} are proposed. Formic acid and the corresponding aldonic acids were detected as the products of oxidation. Diperoiodoargentate(III) oxidizes nitrilotriacetic acid¹⁰ in a mildly basic medium to produce formaldehyde and ammonia. This reaction follows a complex kinetic behaviour and the kinetic experiments indicate that [Ag^{III}(H₃IO₆)(H₂O)₂]⁺ is the reactive silver(III) species involved. Oxidation of glycine^{11(a)}, β-alanine^{11(b)}, L-leucine^{11(c)}, L-isoleucine^{11(d)} and L-proline^{11(e),(f)} leads to the formation of reaction products like NH₄⁺, CO₂ and the corresponding aldehydes. The oxidation of amino acids by Ag^{III} occurs through the intermediate formation of a complex between the reactants followed by decomposition in the slow step. There are also reports on the oxidation involving pharmaceutical drugs viz. paracetamol^{12(a)} and aspirin^{12(b),(c)} by diperoiodoargentate(III). However using bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) as oxidant large amount of kinetic data are available which are mentioned in the results section of this article. Ditelluratoargentate(III) which exhibits diamagnetism has been characterized to [Ag(H₂TeO₆)]⁵⁻ in which two oxygen atoms for each H₂TeO₆ entity is coordinated with silver(III) atom in a square planar configuration.

It might be of interest to correlate different redox processes involving bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) and then to compare the results obtained earlier with the oxidations of the same organic reducing agents by this oxidant. This review is devoted to detailed discussions and correlations of the oxidations of some organic compounds by this oxidant in alkaline medium.

Previous work

Investigation of silver(II) reactions with a variety of reducing agents indicate that either silver(III) or silver(II) can be the oxidant¹³⁻¹⁵. It has been established¹⁶⁻²⁰ that trivalent silver exists as AgO⁺ in acid solution ([H⁺] = 1.5 to 6.0 mol dm⁻³).

The decomposition of Ag²⁺ in solutions has been shown to proceed^{17,21} according to the following steps.

The well-known characterized silver(III) compounds include mixed valent²² silver oxide, the paramagnetic and octahedral M₂AgF₆²³, complexes derived from periodate and tellurate^{7,24}, tetraazamacrocycles porphyrins²⁵, porphyrins²⁶, biguanides²⁷, phosphines, arsines^{28,29}, polypeptides³⁰, hydroxo and other oxo anions³¹.

Since AgO is diamagnetic, chemical evidence rules out the possibility of it being a peroxide. Neutron diffraction has shown³² that it is Ag^IAg^{III}O₂, since there are two types of silver atoms in the lattice, one with linear coordination to two oxygen atoms, Ag^I and the other square planar with respect to oxygen, Ag^{III}. When AgO is dissolved in acid, silver(II) is formed, probably according to the equation,

The preparation of the Ag(OH)₄⁻ ion generally involved anodic oxidation of silver metal in basic media^{7,24}. The stability of Ag(OH)₄⁻ depends on the strength of the base. The ion has life < 30 min in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ OH⁻ and when a solution at 303 K is rapidly brought to pH = 11, decomposition occurs within 1 or 2 s. The product of decomposition in alkaline solution is AgO. A kinetic study of the acid initiated reduction has been reported by Kirschenbaum *et al.*³³. Because it is a low-spin, square planar d⁸ system Ag(OH)₄⁻ can undergo inner sphere redox reaction either by a ligand replacement or via electron transfer through a five coordinated intermediate.

Kirschenbaum *et al.* studied the kinetics of oxidation of hydrogen peroxide³⁴, azide³⁵, nitrite³⁶, sulphite³⁶, thiosulphate³⁷, hypophosphite³⁸, arsenite³⁹, 4-*t*-butyl-phenolate anion⁴⁰, [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻, MnO₄²⁻⁴¹, [Mo(CN)₈]⁴⁻ and thiourea⁴² by Ag(OH)₄⁻ in alkaline medium.

The oxidation of hydrogen peroxide by silver(III) in strongly alkaline media has been studied³⁴ by stopped flow spectrophotometry. The reaction is first order in [Ag^{III}], [HO₂⁻] and [OH⁻]. The form of the rate law and the activation parameters suggest the formation of a 5-coordinated intermediate of the form [Ag(OH)₄O₂H]²⁻.

The reaction between tetrahydroxoargentate(III) ion and azide³⁵ ion proceeds via the formation of a monoazido-silver(III) complex which undergoes internal two-electron transfer only after reaction with an additional N₃⁻.

Ag(OH)₄⁻ failed to oxidize³⁶ NO₂⁻ even in 1 mol dm⁻³ solution of sodium nitrite and this may be due to the unfavorable charge interaction between Ag(OH)₄⁻ and NO₂⁻. Since N^{III} has no vacant acceptor orbital, an oxygen atom transfer path is unlikely.

The reduction of [Ag(OH)₄]⁻ by sulphite ion to give silver(I) and sulphate in strong base has been studied³⁶.

The reaction of [Ag(OH)₄]⁻ with potentially an eight electron reductant, S₂O₃²⁻ was studied in alkaline medium³⁷. The neutral species S₂O₃, which is generated by two-electron oxidation of thiosulphate ion, decomposes to form other reactive sulphur moieties, designated as S_i, which may include sulphite and sulphonylic acid anion. The steps of the reaction are,

The measured 1 : 1 stoichiometry, the simple kinetics, and lack of evidence, either kinetic or spectral, of an intermediate species indicate a one step two electron redox process in the oxidation of hypophosphite ion³⁸.

The kinetics of oxidation of various inorganic and or-

ganic substrates by ethylene bis(biguanide)silver(III) cation have been studied in acid medium⁴³⁻⁴⁷. The reducing substrates used are H₃PO₂⁴³, H₂O₂⁴⁴, hydrazinium ion⁴⁵, nitrite ion⁴⁶, ethanol⁴⁷, methanol⁴⁷ and benzyl alcohol⁴⁷ have been reported.

The reaction of NO₂⁻ ion with Ag^{III} have been studied⁴⁶ in the pH range (1 to 7.5). The reaction is first order with respect to both the reactants. The reaction was suggested to proceed through four parallel paths.

The electron transfer from N₃⁻ to ditelluratoargentate(III) have been carried out in an alkaline medium⁴⁸. The [OH⁻] was varied in the range (0.01-0.2) mol dm⁻³, keeping the ionic strength constant at 0.95 mol dm⁻³. The reaction is first order with respect to [Ag^{III}] but the order with respect to [N₃⁻] is complex. The rate constant decreases with increase in alkali concentration. Silver(III) is reduced⁴⁸ by N₃⁻ in one-step two electron process according to the reaction steps (25-28).

The reaction mechanism indicates that N₃⁻ reacts with ditelluratoargentate(III) through initial complex formation between the reactants followed by decomposition of the

complex to N₂, as one of the reaction products. In addition to N₂ a black residue was also obtained which was analyzed and found to contain 87% silver (88% calculated for AgO). This residue was diamagnetic mixture of Ag^I and Ag^{III} and rules out the possibility of formation of d⁹ silver(II). The black precipitate was dissolved in dil. HNO₃ which gave a yellow precipitate of AgI with KI. The reaction⁴⁸ obeys the following rate law :

$$-\frac{1}{[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}]} \frac{d[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_1 [\text{N}_3^-]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_1 [\text{N}_3^-]} \quad (\text{I})$$

The K₁ and k₁ values were found to be 0.486 ± 0.02 and (0.217 ± 0.01) × 10⁻³ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 303 K, respectively. The values of ΔH⁰ and ΔS⁰ associated with the equilibrium step are 31 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹ and 24 ± 7 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, whereas for the rate-determining step the values of ΔH[#] and ΔS[#] are 68 ± 1 kJ mol⁻¹ and -91 ± 4 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Results

The kinetic and mechanistic feature of the oxidations of some organic compounds viz. alkanols, aryl alcohols, diols, α- and β-glycerophosphates, aldehydes (aliphatic, aromatic, heterocyclic) and α,β-unsaturated compounds by bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) have been studied in aqueous or aquo-organic media.

The oxidation of alkanols^{49(a)} and some aryl alcohols^{50(a)} by bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) have been studied in an alkaline medium. The oxidation of alkanols occur according to the following stoichiometric eq. (30), where, R₁ = R₂ = H for methanol; R₁ = H, R₂ = -CH₃ for ethanol; R₁ = R₂ = -CH₃ for isopropanol.

The reactions are first order each in [Ag^{III}] and [R₁R₂CHOH], but the rate is independent of [OH⁻]. Silver(III) is reduced by the alcohols to give free radicals and silver(II).

Silver(II) which is generated in the slow step disproportionates to give silver(I) and silver(III).

The formation of intermediate free radicals is supported by the observed polymeric suspension in the presence of acrylonitrile. Benzyl alcohol and some substituted benzyl alcohols (XC₆H₄CH₂OH, where X = -NO₂, -Cl and -OMe) are oxidized^{50(a)} to the respective substituted aldehydes.

The mechanism of the oxidation of some vicinal diols such as ethylene glycol, butane-2,3-diol, pinacol and propane-1,2-diol by bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) was studied⁵¹ in an alkaline medium. The oxidation of diols occur as shown in eq. (35), where, R₁ = R₂ = H for ethylene glycol; R₁ = R₂ = -CH₃ for pinacol; R₁ = H, R₂ = -CH₃ for butane-2,3-diol.

The reaction has been shown⁵¹ to occur through the generation of free radical and silver(II) followed by the reaction of free radical with another silver(III) to give carbonyl compounds via C-C bond cleavage.

Oxidative behavior and relative reactivities of two-isomers of glycerophosphates namely α- and β-glycerophosphates towards bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) were studied⁵² in alkaline medium over the temperature range 303-318 K. The values of k_{obs} were independent of the initial [Ag^{III}] in the range of (0.5-2.5) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, but the rate was directly proportional to both [glycerophosphates]. The pseudo-first order rate constant increases with increase of [OH⁻] in the range (2.5-25) ×

10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} with the α -isomer whereas it is independent of $[\text{OH}^-]$ with β -glycerophosphate. The electron transfer⁵² from α -glycerophosphate to silver(III) may occur according to the Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1

followed by (43) and (44)

Scheme 2

However, since hydroxide ion has no effect on the reaction rate of β -glycerophosphate the reaction between β -glycerophosphate and silver(III) takes place with the intermediate formation of free radicals⁵² according to the Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

The reaction mechanism shows that both the glycerophosphates are oxidized to their respective phosphoglyceraldehydes and silver(II).

The reactivity of α, β -unsaturated compounds such as acrylonitrile ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCN}$), acrylamide ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCONH}_2$) and acrylate ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOO}^-$) towards bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) have been investigated^{53(a)} in an alkaline medium. Under the kinetic conditions, the substrates are oxidized to give the respective diols according to the stoichiometric equation,

The reduction of silver(III) appear to involve one-step two-electron change with the intermediate formation of carbocation^{53(a)} according to the following steps.

The reaction mechanism shows^{53(a)} that OH^- ion accelerated the reaction rate which is supported by the following rate expression :

$$-d[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}]/dt = k_3'[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}] [\alpha, \beta\text{-unsaturated compound}] [\text{OH}^-] \quad (\text{II})$$

The k_3' values for the oxidation of $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCN}$, $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCONH}_2$ and $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOO}^-$ are 1.49×10^{-2} , 1.07×10^{-2} and 0.80×10^{-2} mol⁻² dm⁶ s⁻¹, respectively at 303 K. α, β -Unsaturated compounds react with silver(III) in the order : $-\text{CN} > -\text{CONH}_2 > -\text{COO}^-$. The observation is similar to those made earlier with Pt^{IV} 53(b) and bromate^{53(c)} ion oxidations of the same substrates.

In connection with the oxidations of alkanols, carbonyl compounds were found to be the oxidation products and their concentrations were too low to be oxidized. However at $[\text{RCHO}] > 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ oxidations of aldehydes occur at appreciable rates. The reduction of bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) by some aliphatic, heterocyclic and aromatic aldehydes have been investigated⁵⁴ in (0.016–0.16) mol dm⁻³ $[\text{OH}^-]$. The oxidation

of aliphatic aldehydes and 2-furaldehyde occur as shown in eq. (53), where R = aliphatic (-H, -Me, -CH₂Me, -CHMe₂).

The reactions are first-order in [RCHO] and [Ag^{III}]. However, the rate was found to be independent of [OH⁻]. Since the rate of the reactions is independent of [OH⁻], the possibility of the oxidations of RCH(OH)O⁻ by [Ag^{III}(H₂TeO₆)₂]⁵⁻ has been ruled out. The oxidation products are obtained⁵⁴ through the intermediate formations of RC[•]=O and RC⁺=O in successive steps. The latter is converted in alkaline medium to give carboxylate ions. The steps of the reactions are :

Scheme 4

The reaction possibly occurs by a complementary mechanism via Scheme 4, although the other possibility (Scheme 5) can not be totally ruled out⁵⁴.

followed by step (56)

Scheme 5

Some aromatic aldehydes (XC₆H₄CHO, where X = -H, -NO₂, -Cl and -OMe) are also oxidized by this oxidant in alkaline medium⁵⁴ according to the equation,

The influence of substituents on the rates have been studied under comparable condition of experiments in *t*-butanol (15% v/v). The electron withdrawing substituents facilitate the rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde whereas electron donating substituents have opposite effect.

Discussion

The values of second-order rate constant for the oxidations of some reducing substrates by Ag^{III} complex are recorded in Table 1. The important features concerning the reduction of Ag^{III} by alcohols^{49(a),50(a)} are as follows. Since the rate is directly proportional to [R₁R₂CHOH]

Table 1. Values of second-order rate constants for the oxidation of different organic substrates by bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III)

Substrate	10 ² k ₂ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Ref.	Substrate	10 ² k ₂ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Ref.
Methanol	0.197 ± 0.01 ^a	49(a)	Formaldehyde	3.12 ± 0.15	54
Ethanol	0.23 ± 0.01 ^a	49(a)	Acetaldehyde	11.6 ± 0.6	54
Isopropanol	0.177 ± 0.01 ^a	49(a)	Propionaldehyde	29.7 ± 1.4	54
Benzyl alcohol	13.3 ± 0.6 ^a	49(a)	Isobutyraldehyde	41.2 ± 1.6	54
	3.19 ± 0.1 ^b	50(a)			
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzyl alcohol	3.32 ± 0.14 ^c	50(a)	2-Furaldehyde	0.98 ± 0.03	54
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzyl alcohol	3.83 ± 0.15 ^c	50(a)	Benzaldehyde	0.27 ± 0.008 ^d	54
				0.94 ± 0.04 ^a	54
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzyl alcohol	4.09 ± 0.23 ^c	50(a)	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	1.37 ± 0.07 ^a	54
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzyl alcohol	2.07 ± 0.12 ^c	50(a)	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	0.99 ± 0.02 ^a	54
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzyl alcohol	2.3 ± 0.06 ^c	50(a)	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	1.08 ± 0.04 ^a	54
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzyl alcohol	2.98 ± 0.14 ^c	50(a)	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	0.35 ± 0.01 ^a	54
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzyl alcohol	1.79 ± 0.07 ^c	50(a)	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	0.25 ± 0.02 ^a	54
<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzyl alcohol	2.17 ± 0.13 ^c	50(a)	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	0.13 ± 0.004 ^a	54
<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzyl alcohol	2.53 ± 0.06 ^c	50(a)	<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	0.25 ± 0.01 ^a	54

Table-1 (contd.)

Ethylene glycol	1.84 ± 0.06	51	<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	0.19 ± 0.007 ^a	54
Butane-2,3-diol	12.2 ± 0.4	51	<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	0.12 ± 0.006 ^a	54
Pinacol	6.66 ± 0.24	51	Acrylonitrile	0.139 ± 0.005 ^e	53(a)
Propane-1,2-diol	4.45 ± 0.13	51	Acrylamide	0.089 ± 0.002 ^e	53(a)
α-Glycerophosphate	6.29 ± 0.25 ^f	52	Acrylic acid	0.072 ± 0.003 ^e	53(a)
β-Glycerophosphate	1.12 ± 0.06 ^f	52			

The oxidation of aromatic aldehydes and substituted benzyl alcohols were studied in 15% *t*-butyl alcohol. The values of $k_2 (= k_{\text{obs}}/[S])$ were obtained at 298 K unless stated otherwise. ^aAt 313 K. ^bIn 15% *tert*-butyl alcohol. ^cAt 318 K. ^dIn aqueous medium. ^eAt $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.24 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. ^fAt 303 K and $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

and $[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ but independent of $[\text{OH}^-]$, it is suggested that the major reaction path is taking place between Ag^{III} and molecular alcohol rather than alkoxide^{49(a)}. The rate of oxidations of methanol-d and ethanol-d by silver(III) were found to be practically same under similar experimental conditions. These results suggest that the O-H bond fission is not significant in the rate limiting step (eq. 31)^{49(a),50(a)}. The rate of oxidation of alkanols follows the order : ethanol > methanol > isopropanol which confirms the observation made earlier with Ir^{IV} ^{49(b)} and Au^{III} ^{50(c)} oxidation of the same substrates in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer medium. The reaction occurs by the rupture of C-H bond to give free radical as shown in Scheme 6.

$\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}$ are formed during the oxidations of aryl alcohols in alcohol-water mixture. Moreover, irrespective of whether the radical is $\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\dot{\text{C}}\text{OH}$ or $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}$ further oxidation of the intermediates to give products occur^{50(a)} as shown in step (32). Again benzyl alcohol and substituted benzyl alcohols are oxidized to give benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes^{50(a)}. The yields of DNP-derivatives of the oxidation product are recorded in Table 2 and results are also plotted in Fig. 1, which indicate that further oxidation of benzaldehyde to benzoic acid is insignificant during experimental study. The results indicate that unsubstituted benzyl alcohol reacts with Ag^{III} at a faster rate than benzhydrol and this slow

Scheme 6

On the other hand spin trapping studies of the photo-oxidation of benzyl alcohol by hexachlorometallate(IV) ($\text{M}^{\text{IV}} = \text{Pt}, \text{Pd}$ and Ir) have shown^{50(b)} the formation of $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\dot{\text{O}}$ in pure alcoholic medium, however, $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}$ is formed in alcohol-water mixture either directly or via secondary reactions of $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\dot{\text{O}}$ by the H atom transfer reaction or the isomerisation reaction.

Thus, it is suggested that the radical intermediates

rate in benzhydrol probably due to the steric hindrance of the second phenyl group on the carbinol carbon makes the reactions with Ag^{III} less favourable. Among the different nuclear-substituted benzyl alcohols, the electron withdrawing groups react at much faster rates than the corresponding electron donating groups. The rate of oxidations of benzyl alcohol as well as substituted benzyl alcohols^{50(a)} follow the order : $-\text{NO}_2 > -\text{H} > -\text{Cl} > -\text{OMe}$.

The kinetic evidence for the formation of a 1 : 1 intermediate complex between the diol and Ag^{III} ⁵¹ is insignificant. The oxidation of ethylene glycol and pinacol by bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III)⁵¹ leads to the formation of formaldehyde and acetone whereas acetaldehyde is formed as the oxidation product of butane-2,3-

Table 2. Yields of the 2,4-DNP derivatives of the oxidation products of alkanols, aromatic alcohols and diols by both bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) and bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III)

Substrate	%2,4-DNP derivatives with		Ref.
	Ag ^{III}	Cu ^{III}	
Methanol	45	45	49(a)
Ethanol	60	60	49(a)
Isopropanol	60	60	49(a)
Benzyl alcohol (aq)	90	94	49(a)
Benzyl alcohol	58	60	50(a)
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzyl alcohol	36	48	50(a)
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzyl alcohol	51	52	50(a)
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzyl alcohol	52	55	50(a)
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzyl alcohol	54	56	50(a)
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzyl alcohol	57	58	50(a)
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzyl alcohol	59	61	50(a)
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzyl alcohol	60	62	50(a)
<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzyl alcohol	64	66	50(a)
<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzyl alcohol	71	74	50(a)
Ethylene glycol	82	88	51
Butane-2,3-diol	88	90	51
Pinacol	64	70	51

Oxidation involving benzyl alcohol and substituted benzyl alcohols were studied in 15% *t*-butyl alcohol.

Fig. 1. Variation of % yield of the reaction product with time for the oxidations of benzyl alcohol^{50(a)} by (A) : copper(II) and (B) : silver(III).

diol under similar experimental conditions indicating that initial attack of Ag^{III} on H-C-O-H (hydroxyl hydrogen) rather than H-C-O-H (α -H) occurs in the reaction mechanism (eq. 36). In the oxidations by silver(III) complex, silver(II) which is generated in the slow step

disproportionates to give silver(I) and silver(III) as shown in eq. (38) where the reaction between $[\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{6-}$ and $\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{C}(\text{OH})\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{C}\ddot{\text{O}}$ is discounted. Thus alkanols and aryl alcohols are oxidized to give carbonyl compounds via C-H bond rupture whereas diols are oxidized initially by O-H bond fission followed by C-C bond rupture to give reaction products⁵¹. These are in conformity with the observations made earlier during the oxidations of these substrates by chromium(VI) in acidic medium⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷. The yields of the 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivatives of the oxidation products of the reactions are recorded in Table 2.

Kinetics of the oxidations of 1,2-butanediol, 1,3-propylene glycol, 1,3-butylene glycol and polyhydric alcohols by dihydroxy ditelluratoargentate(III) have been reported in alkaline medium^{58,59}. The reactions have been shown to occur through the intermediate formation of adduct between the reactants to give reaction products tested by the preparation of 2,4-DNP derivatives. It is still to be ascertained whether these reactions occur by C-H bond fission or via O-H bond rupture to give oxidation products.

Disodium salts of glycerophosphates exist as dinegative

ions in aqueous solution. The apparent ionization constants of glycerolphosphates are known⁶⁰. The pK_a and pK_b of α -glycerophosphoric acid are 1.40 and 6.44 whereas the corresponding values of β -glycerophosphoric acid are 1.37 and 6.34 respectively. Glycerophosphates are oxidized by metal ions like MnO_4^- ⁶¹, $IrCl_6^{2-}$ ⁶² and OsO_4^{2-} ⁶³ under different experimental conditions. When glycerophosphates are oxidized by MnO_4^- in high acidic medium⁶¹ (1.0 M $HClO_4$), the respective dianions are protonated which react with MnO_4^- . On the other hand, when oxidized by $IrCl_6^{2-}$ in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer medium (pH 4.57) both $ROPO_3H^-$ and $ROPO_3^{2-}$ (where $R = CH_2CH(OH)CH_2OH$ for α -glycerophosphate and $R = CH(CH_2OH)_2$ for β -glycerophosphate) are oxidized⁶². α -Glycerophosphate is oxidized by osmium(VIII)⁶³ through the intermediate formation of complex in alkaline medium whereas for β -glycerophosphate there is no evidence for any intermediate complex formation between the reactants. A one step two electron transfer process occurs leading to the formation of 3-phosphoglyceraldehyde and 2-phosphoglyceraldehyde in the respective reactions. On the other hand there is no experimental evidence for intermediate formation of complex between α -glycerophosphate with bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III)⁵². The reaction involving α -glycerophosphate and bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) proceed by the attack of the negative alkoxide ion to give a five coordinated silver(III) compound which ultimately changes the bond length of the two reactants thereby facilitating the electron transfer to yield the products of reaction (Schemes 1 and 2). The following rate expression was derived for the oxidation of α -glycerophosphate.

$$-d[Ag^{III}]/dt = \frac{k_3 + k_2 K_2 [OH^-][RCH_2OH][Ag^{III}]}{1 + K_2 [OH^-]} \quad (III)$$

Since K_2 is small, $1 \gg K_2 [OH^-]$, the eq. (III) changes to,

$$k_2' = a + b [OH^-] \quad (IV)$$

where, $a = k_3$ and $b = k_2 K_2$. From the plots of k_2' against $[OH^-]$ at different temperatures, the values of 'a' and 'b' were calculated. The value of k_2' in the oxidation of β -glycerophosphate is $6.90 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35 °C and ionic strength of 0.25 mol dm^{-3} , respectively whereas the extrapolated value of the same at $[OH^-] = 0$

from α -glycerophosphate is $7.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at the same temperature and ionic strength. A comparison of the rate constant between the $[OH^-]$ independent path for α -substrate and that for β -substrate indicates that they are not widely different which justify the rate expression. The values of ΔH_a^\ddagger and ΔS_a^\ddagger for the alkali independent paths are $91 \pm 4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $28 \pm 13 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and ΔH_b^\ddagger and ΔS_b^\ddagger for the alkali dependent path are $123 \pm 6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $150 \pm 19 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. As compared to α -glycerophosphate, the oxidation of β -glycerophosphate is characterized by simple rate expression. 1H NMR spectra of the glycerophosphate in D_2O were also recorded which gave peaks for the $>CH_2$ (δ ppm 3.60–3.67) and C–OH (δ ppm 3.45–3.51) for the α -compound, whereas for the β -compound only the peak for $>CH_2$ (δ ppm 3.52–3.53) was obtained. The distinctively different 1H NMR spectral pattern⁵² for the α - and β -compounds corroborates the experimental observation as well as the suggested mechanism. The reaction mixture when allowed to stand for one hour, a black precipitate was obtained in each reaction which was filtered off. On acidification of the filtrate with concentrated HCl and then addition of excess aqueous 2,4-DNP/HCl gave yellow precipitate. The m.p. of the derivatives of the respective glycerophosphates were determined which were much higher than those of 2,4-DNP, and its derivatives with L-glyceraldehyde and D-glyceraldehyde. Glycerophosphates are oxidized to their respective phosphoglyceraldehyde. The EPR spectrum of the black silver compound was recorded. The g -value was found to be 2.1870 as compared to that of 2.0023 for free electron. The magnetic moment at room temperature (30 °C) of the black compound was found to be 1.34 B.M. These indicate that silver(III) which is reduced to give black silver compound exhibits paramagnetic behavior.

The cyclic voltammograms of acrylonitrile, acrylamide and acrylic acid clearly indicate that the substrates are oxidized^{53(a)} in a potential range of -0.225 to 0.35 V at 298 K. A cyclic voltammogram of Ag^{III} exhibited an irreversible reduction at -0.65 V at 298 K which indicated that silver(III) species undergoes a one-step two-electron transfer process. The reaction takes place through the formation of intermediate state formed between $[Ag^{III}(H_2TeO_6)_2]^{5-}$ and $HOCH_2\bar{C}HX$ which decomposes to give carbonium ion Ag^I complex in a one step two

Scheme 7

electron process^{53(a)} (Scheme 7).

Silver(I) complex which is obtained decomposes on standing to give black precipitate of Ag₂O and the substrates are oxidized by silver(III) to give diols by inner-sphere mechanistic path. After the kinetic experiments, the reaction mixture were filtered to remove insoluble black product^{53(a)}. The filtrate was dried in lyophiliser and the crude mass was washed with EtOAc in the oxidation products obtained from acrylonitrile and acrylamide. For acrylate ion, the crude solid mass was acidified (pH ~5-6) and washed with EtOAc. The oxidized product was separated out by column chromatography of the product mixture over silica gel using 4 : 1 EtOAc + EtOH. The IR spectra in the range of 3200-3350 cm⁻¹ clearly indicate the presence of -OH in the oxidation product of the substrates. In addition, bands at 2250 cm⁻¹, 1670 cm⁻¹ and 1718 cm⁻¹ also indicate the presence of -CN, -CONH₂ and -COOH groups in the oxidation product, which confirms that the substrates are oxidized to glyconitrile, glyceramide and glycerate ion respectively. Further, the diols were treated separately with lead tetraacetate and the resulting products gave yellow precipitates with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. The precipitates were filtered, washed, dried and analyzed [m.p. ~166-168 °C, lit. m.p. = 168 °C; Found : C, 40.05; H, 2.80; N, 25.80. Calcd. for C₇H₆N₄O₄ : C, 40.0; H, 2.85; N, 26.6 (%)]. The results indicate that formaldehyde is formed as the reaction product. Again in addition to formaldehyde, XCHO (X = -CN, -CONH₂ and -COOH) is also formed. The product having -CN or -CONH₂ groups on hydrolysis gives glyoxylic acid, which subsequently gives another molecule of formaldehyde on decarboxylation. The absence of bands due to -CN, -CONH₂ and -COOH in the IR spectra of the DNP-derivatives of the respective products also corroborate the above results.

The kinetic evidence for the formation of a 1 : 1 intermediate complex between the RCHO and [Ag^{III}(H₂TeO₆)₂]⁵⁻ is insignificant⁵⁴. The reactions have been carried out in alkaline medium and the rate of each reaction is indepen-

dent of [OH⁻]. The possibility of the reaction of RCH(OH)O⁻ with the oxidants seem unlikely rather unhydrated aldehydes react with the silver(III) to give products. The primary isotope effects indicate^{53(d)} that carbon-hydrogen bond breakage occurs ($k_H/k_D = 5.0$) in the rate determining step during the oxidation of aliphatic aldehyde by transition metal ion oxidant although it is not clear whether the slow step involves hydride ion transfer or hydrogen atom abstraction. However experimental evidence indicate that the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes occurs through the intermediate formation of free radicals⁵⁴. Again of the different aldehydes, the aliphatic aldehydes react at much faster rates than heterocyclic and aromatic aldehydes. The oxidation rates follow the order : Me₂CH- > MeCH₂- > Me- > H- > C₄H₃O- > C₆H₅-. The value of ρ* (susceptibility of the reaction to polar effect)^{64(a)} has been calculated to be -1.61 ($r = 0.9720$) from the plot of log (rate) against σ* (the polar substituent constant). The oxidations of aromatic aldehydes (XC₆H₄CHO) by silver(III) also occur through the intermediate formation of free radicals⁵⁴. The rate of oxidation increases with the electron withdrawing substituents and decreases with the presence of electron-donating substituents. The oxidation rates follow the order : -NO₂ > -H > -Cl > -OMe. A similar observation was also noticed in the oxidation of these aromatic aldehydes by alkaline permanganate^{64(b)}. The values of log k_{obs} were plotted as a function of δ (Hammett substituent constants⁶⁵) in order to verify the effect of substituents. The value of ρ has been calculated to be 0.84 for *meta* and *para* substituted compounds ($r = 0.9096$). Under comparable experimental conditions the pseudo-first order rate constants decreased considerably in benzaldehyde-d₁ than simple benzaldehyde. The values of k_H/k_D is 4.14 which indicates that the reaction occurs via C-H bond fission in the slow step. Although the reactions proceed through the intermediate formation of free radicals, a single two-electron mechanism may also be operative. However, initiation of acrylamide polymerization could be due to a side reaction that generates radicals. The isotope and sub-

stituent effects are consistent with C–H bond cleavage via proton transfer. The reaction mixtures in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by silver(III) were filtered to remove black precipitate. The filtrate obtained in the oxidation of formaldehyde was treated with mercuric chloride, when crystalline precipitates of mercurous chloride appeared indicating for-maldehyde is oxidized to formate ion. The product obtained in the oxidation of acetaldehyde was found to be acetic acid tested by its lanthanum nitrate test. The reaction mixtures with aromatic aldehydes were allowed to stand for 1 h and then filtered to remove any insoluble products. The filtrates were then acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid when white crystals were obtained. The precipitated organic acids of the respective aldehydes were extracted with chloroform. On removal of the solvent, colorless residues of the organic acids were derived. The yields of benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids are recorded in Table 3. The results indicate that the yields of the oxidation products of *p*-substituted benzaldehydes are always higher than those of *m*- and *o*-substituted derivatives. The lower yields of *o*-substituted derivatives may be due to the fact that *o*-substituted benzoic acids are much stronger than *m*- and *p*-substituted compounds. The absence of silver(0) precipitation in large excess of aldehydes has been attributed to increased stability of silver(I) towards unreacted aldehydes.

Table 3. Yields of the oxidation products for the oxidation of different aromatic aldehydes by silver(III) and copper(III) in 30% *t*-butyl alcohol

Substrate	%Yield with Ag ^{III}		Ref.
	complex	complex	
Benzaldehyde	59	68	54
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	62	65	54
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	64	66	54
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	67	68	54
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	75	78	54
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	84	87	54
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	88	90	54
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	70	74	54
<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	75	82	54
<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	80	86	54

The values of ΔS^\ddagger are plotted against ΔH^\ddagger for different reactions. The plots of ΔS^\ddagger vs ΔH^\ddagger exhibit linear relationship (Fig. 2). The oxidation of diols are characterized by higher activation parameters than alkanols (except ethanol), aryl alcohols and aldehydes (except for-

maldehyde and furaldehyde). The bond energies $\epsilon_{C-H} = 414.2$ kJ/mol and $\epsilon_{O-H} = 464.4$ kJ/mol are in accordance with the above findings. Again the activation parameters obtained in the oxidations of α, β -unsaturated compounds are also very high. This may be due to electrostatic repulsion between two similarly charged ions, e.g. $[Ag^{III}(H_2TeO_6)_2]^{5-}$ and $HOCH_2\bar{C}HX$ to form activated complex, thereby increasing energy of activation and hence activation parameters.

Fig. 2. Isokinetic correlation for the oxidations of different organic substrates by ditelluratoargentate(III). Plots of ΔS^\ddagger vs ΔH^\ddagger .

The reactions except α, β -unsaturated compounds have been shown to occur through intermediate formation of free radicals and Ag^{II} . Further reduction of Ag^{II} by free radicals seems unlikely since both are unstable intermediates rather Ag^{II} disproportionates to give Ag^{III} and Ag^I . This is contrary to the observations made earlier in the oxidations of the organic substrates by bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) where copper(III) is reduced to copper(II). However, irrespective of all the organic substrates, bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) reacts at faster rates than the corresponding reactions with bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III). This is supported by the results as shown in Table 4. The results are to be expected since the third ionization potential³⁰ for silver is less than that of copper. Moreover, in cases where Ag^{III}/Ag^{II} ⁶⁶ couples can be compared with Cu^{III}/Cu^{II} ⁶⁷ couples, results indicate that the redox potential for silver is less than that for copper. The existence of Ag^{II} in aqueous medium is well established. A great deal of work has been published on the reduction of Ag^{II} in aqueous medium. The preparation of Ag^{2+} under different conditions indicates that it

Table 4. Values of second-order rate constants for the oxidation of some organic compounds by silver(III) and copper(III) complexes

Substrate	$10^2 k_2^a$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)	$10^2 k_2^b$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Ref.
Methanol	0.197 ± 0.01^c	0.356 ± 0.02	49(a)
Benzylalcohol	3.19 ± 0.01	8.53 ± 0.2	50(a)
Ethylene glycol	1.84 ± 0.06	8.9 ± 0.4^d	51
Acetaldehyde	11.6 ± 0.6	31.2 ± 1.4	54
Benzaldehyde	0.94 ± 0.04	2.25 ± 0.14	54
Acrylic acid	0.072 ± 0.003	0.128 ± 0.005	53(a)

^aOxidation involving silver(III) complex. ^bOxidation involving copper(III) complex. The values of k_2 were obtained at 298 K unless stated otherwise. ^cAt 313 K. ^dAt 283 K.

could be stabilized by the use of strongly acidic solution⁶⁸. Spectrophotometric studies of Ag^{2+} in HClO_4 , HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 have been reported. The reduction potentials (E^0) for the $\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}$ couples have been determined⁶⁹. The values of E^0 are 1.932, 2.00 and 1.453 V in HNO_3 , HClO_4 and H_2SO_4 medium respectively at 25 °C. On the other hand, different values of 1.927 V and 1.970 V have been reported²⁰ in 4.0 mol dm^{-3} HNO_3 and HClO_4 respectively.

The reactions of Ag^{II} with water^{16a} and H_2O_2 ⁷⁰ have been studied. The second-order rate constants for the oxidations of Fe^{II} , V^{IV} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Ce^{III} have been determined. The behavior of metal ions towards Ag^{II} appear to be simple giving the rate equation⁷¹,

$$-d[\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}]/dt = k_4 [\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}] [\text{M}^{\text{n}+}] \quad (\text{V})$$

The oxidation of dithionate by Ag^{II} in perchloric acid solution⁷² in the presence of excess Ag^{I} yields sulphate and follows straight forward rate equation,

$$-d[\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}]/dt = k_5 [\text{H}^+] [\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_6^{2-}] \quad (\text{VI})$$

Silver(II) compounds react with carboxylic acids to form Ag^{I} , CO_2 and a variety of organic oxidation products⁷³ according to the eq. (62),

where, $\text{R}(\text{-H})_{\text{OX}}$ represents the organic oxidation products. The reactions obey the following rate law

$$-d[\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}]/dt = k_6 [\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}] [\text{RCO}_2\text{H}] \quad (\text{VII})$$

For the carboxylic acids the electron transfer is easier which increases the electron density at the reaction centre. Ag^{2+} attacks the OH group of the acid as shown in Scheme 8.

Scheme 8

Rate constants for intra-molecular electron transfer reactions of Ag^{II} complexes with ethylene glycol, glycine, pivalic acid and succinate have been determined^{74,75}. Numerous silver(II) complexes with heterocyclic nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur ligands have been prepared in their solid states. The compounds have been characterized by different physical methods like magnetic and ESR measurements. The details have been reviewed¹.

The reactivities of bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) towards different inorganic and organic substrates in alkaline medium have been studied earlier and the details have been reviewed⁷⁶. The present review which deals with silver(III) complex in alkaline medium has also presented different aspects of reactions. The reactivities of some inorganic and organic substrates towards gold(III) have been studied and reviewed earlier⁷⁷. All these reactions with gold(III) are slow in high acid medium (> 0.1 mol dm^{-3}) but takes place at measurable rates at acidities ($<< 0.1$ mol dm^{-3}). Different species of gold(III) like AuCl_4^- , $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH}_2)$ and $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-$ participate in these reactions and the reactions are characterized by complex kinetic rate expressions unlike copper(III) and silver(III) oxidations which follow simple kinetic pattern. Hence the rate constants of gold(III) oxidations cannot be compared with those obtained earlier with copper(III) and silver(III). Regardless of which oxidant is used, one point of information has been obtained with certainty that all the reactions occur by inner-sphere mechanism.

Experimental

The bis(dihydrogentellurato)argentate(III) solution was prepared⁵ in alkaline medium by oxidation of silver nitrate with potassium persulphate in the presence of potassium tellurite. The absorption of silver(III) solution were studied in the concentration range of $(1.75\text{--}26.25) \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} . Each spectrum of ditelluratoargentate(III) exhibited an absorption maxima at 266 nm and 350 nm, respectively.

The silver(III) complex was estimated by mixing an aliquot from the stock solution with sufficient arsenite solution. The mixture was allowed to stand for ~ 5 min and then acidified with dil. H_2SO_4 until the solution be-

came colorless. Finally, NaHCO₃ solution was added and the unconsumed arsenite back titrated against standard I₂ solution using starch as indicator.

The rate of decrease of silver(III) in alkaline medium was followed titrimetrically under pseudo-first order conditions. Solutions of Ag^{III} and the mixture containing substrate and OH⁻ were separately thermostatted (± 0.1 °C) for nearly 1 h before the kinetic run. The reaction was started by adding the oxidant to the other reactants and was followed by transferring aliquots of the mixture at different time intervals into a known excess of sodium arsenite solution. The unconsumed arsenite was acidified with dilute sulfuric acid and titrated against standard iodine using starch as indicator.

Absorbances were measured on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were studied on a Perkin-Elmer 298 spectrometer. EPR spectra were recorded with a Varian EPR spectrometer. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded by a Bio-Analytical Systems (BAS) CV-27 instrument in a dry Ar atmosphere using a three-electrode configuration. Thermogravimetric analysis was performed in a Shimadzu Corporation (Japan) TG50 in a normal atmospheric environment.

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